

PARTICLE HYBRIDIZED SEALION OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM (PHSLA) - A NOVEL OBJECT DETECTION METHOD

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Abstract

Assistive innovation empowers individuals to accomplish autonomy while performing household tasks, and it improves their overall quality of life as well. The purpose of this research is to propose model for object detection in an indoor environment for visually challenged persons. Initially, the input image from real-world scenario is subjected to pre-processing via wiener filtering. Subsequently, segmentation is carried out by the novel proposed Multi-Kernel K-means clustering model and SURF, SIFT, Shape based features via canny edges & Gradient features via HOG were extracted from segmented source. The optimal features are selected from extracted features by a new hybrid algorithm referred as Particle Hybridized SeaLion Optimization Algorithm (PHSLA) and selected optimal features are classified using Optimized Convolutional Neural Network (OCNN) for detecting the object. Final Comparative study is carried out between the proposed hybrid model and existing work. It was observed that CNN and PHSLA revived 98% accuracy in classification of real time objects.

Keywords: Object Detection; Visually Challenged (VC); Multi-Kernal K-means; SIFT; SURF; PHSLA; OCNN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Great vision is a valuable blessing, and it is one of the significant human facilities for gaining information from their circumstances. Yet, tragically vision loss is turning out to be regular nowadays. As per the report by WHO, 314 million individuals experience the ill effects of visual disability. Due to various medical conditions, the uncorrected refractive blunders or the eye ailments are said to be the typical reasons behind the visual impairment [1]. 45 million people are visually challenged (blind) out of the 314 million people who are outwardly disabled [2 – 5]. Visual data is the major source of most of the navigational undertakings, so outwardly impeded people are at a detriment because of the absence of adequate data about their general condition: with the ongoing advances in comprehensive innovation, it is conceivable to stretch out the assistance given to Visually Challenged (VC) individuals as far as their versatility is concerned. Further, due to the maturing populace, visual impairment has become ever-expanding and pervasive. As people getting older, there is a higher danger of visual hindrance that expands the trouble of independent portability. The absence of suitable assistive gadgets for these people makes them excessively dependent on their kith and kin [6-8]. Visual

impairment and visual impedances represent a parsing need to create new programmed frameworks to help people with visual disabilities. The programmed devices may indeed be useful in developing a new application for identifying and interpreting indoor articles in their regular indoor track [9-13].

2. RELATED WORK

Despite the fact that innovation has made considerable progress, self-governing navigates to overwhelm the challenge. At this time, the walking stick is the more commonly recognized self-navigator for the visually impaired. Though ultrasonic sensors have been added to walking sticks [14], these detectors only work well for a few meters at most. Such advances include the use of a PC vision framework that can identify the patterns on the walkway and assist the user in navigating and exploring the objects. Some interesting work summarizing some characteristics and obstacles of existing works on object identification and navigation for visually challenged people that have been published in the literature. The Retina Net [15] has high detection efficiency when it comes to indoor materials. If the precision (mAP) is strengthened further, this approach could be much stronger. The single-shot multi box detector framework improves detection sensitivity and latency, making it suitable for real-time operations. For greater efficiency, this methodology may employ high-speed complex algorithms. Nav Can increases obstacle-free navigation efficiency, and machine learning algorithms can be implemented for user behavior profiling. Furthermore, the electromagnetic sensor in [16] is noise resistant, and the echoes here are much higher than the noise threshold, which is a disadvantage. Item identification for navigation is made easier with the 3-D object recognition system [17]. The object recognition code can be given a lot of consideration in this approach to form a full navigation scheme. Furthermore, CNN in [18] allows the unit to be used both indoors and outdoors. However, for accurate target recognition, this approach may make use of a lighter-weight neural network. The MSF approach in [19] is computationally simple, but it isn't suitable for real-time applications. The cost-effective mobile phone-based device solution in is both cost-effective and noise-resistant. Furthermore, features such as "LBP, Gabor, and Histogram-based features", among others, can be used to differentiate between different types of obstacles present, such as a chair, vehicle, or human, to improve the efficiency of VC [20].

Moreover recognizing unambiguous indoor objects represents some major issues as numerous items are in attendance, likewise, a few articles are blocked with different items and others can't be identified in view of the lighting conditions. These issues together make up the mechanism of object detection. Moreover, being able to navigate from one spot to the next presents a significant part of our day-by-day lives [21 - 23]. These devices, on the other hand, could only navigate through a spatial domain; they couldn't solve the problem of exploring a specific article or region in a route [24]. Recognizing and locating indoor articles in an info picture presents a significant application that makes PCs ready to comprehend the contiguous environment. Further, to build up object detection as well as a navigation-based application for the visually impaired, it is essential to understand the article that we need to perceive on a par with the human mind. The classification and regression are primary areas where the object

recognition and navigation problem were clearly separated. The article type is determined by the classification section, while the regression section determines the object box coordinates. The recognition step is obtained during the classification process by extracting the significant features from the information photo or video. This research serves as the foundation for a variety of computer vision activities such as object recognition, segmentation, and street sign detection. Faster-RCNN and cover RCNN are two-phase object identifiers that use the RPN to construct ROIs in the first stage, and then pass the ROIs to the second stage for object classification and bbox regression. However, the shortcoming of two-phase object detectors is that they are extremely moderate in any case. Again, the one-phase object locators as SSD and YOLO try not to introduce a pre-treatment for forefront up-and-comers however they treat the article location issue as a basic regression issue. Image recognition is one of the most significant pieces of CAD innovation. The optimization algorithms [25-26] are playing a major role in the object detection approach.

The major contribution of this research work is brought in line with two important segments where at first the efforts were targeted towards introducing a Multi-Kernal K-means algorithm for the segmentation process and introducing a Weight-Optimized CNN model. The weight of CNN is optimized by a new Partial Hybridized SeaLion Optimization Algorithm (PHSLA), which is a conceptual blending of standard PSO and SLnO, respectively. The rest of this paper is organized into five sections where Section 2 tells about the proposed object detection model for blind and visually challenged people. The pre-processing and segmentation with multi-kernel k-means are depicted in Section 3. Multi-feature extraction: SURF, SIFT, SHAPE, and gradient feature is portrayed in Section 4. Section 5 tells about object detection via optimized CNN using PHSLA. The results acquired with the proposed work are discussed in Section 6. This paper is concluded in Section 7.

3. PROPOSED OBJECT DETECTION MODEL FOR VISUALLY CHALLENGED PEOPLE (ODMVC)

The proposed model focuses on an indoor environment where the objects in the scene are stationary and moreover the scene is captured by the head mounted scene acquisition device posting data to the connected systems for the purpose of real time object detection and transliteration in audio in to ear buds of the person. In order to handle the complexity in object detection mechanism, the presented research work provides the detailed discussion over black-box functionality of the proposed system. The novel Object Detection Model for Visually Impaired persons with an objective of real-time assistance to visually impaired / challenged person through robust, fast and accurate object classification mechanism. Assistive innovation allows visually challenged people to accomplish independence while doing their everyday chores, and hence increases their standard of living. In this research work, a novel object detection model is designed by following five major phases: “pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, optimal feature selection, and object detection”. The architectural implementation of the proposed object recognition paradigm for visually disabled people can be seen in Fig. 1. and function of each phase discussed as:

Figure 1: Architecture of the Proposed System

3.1 Pre-Processing via Weiner Filter

Initially, the input image I_{inp} is subjected to pre-processing for enhancing the image structure at different scales. Here, the pre-processing is accomplished with the aid of the wiener filtering with the intent of removing the unwanted artifacts from I_{inp} image and pre-processed image is represented by I_{pre} . Unwanted artifacts remove by wiener filtering if not handled appropriately contributes in errors towards determination of feature sets. The choice of Weiner filter is due to the highest PSNR (in dB) thus having the lowest MSE (in dB), as compared to other compatible ones [27]. Furthermore, the Weiner filter performs the optimal noise smoothing and inverse filtering tradeoffs.

The input image is the combination of the original image and the noisy image as Eq. (1),

$$I_{inp}(t, u) = org(t, u) + nos(t, u) \quad (1)$$

Where (t, u) , represents the pixel position in Image I. In the input image we are using Weiner filter and obtaining the output $O(t, u)$ the standard mathematical equation for the Weiner filter is represented by Eq. (2) providing degradation function $H(t, u)$ also called Optical Transfer function (OTF)

$$H(t, u) = \frac{P_D(t, u)}{P_D(t, u) + P_N(t, u)} \quad (2)$$

Where: $P_N(t, u)$ is the power spectrum of noise $nos(t, u)$ and $P_D(t, u)$ is the power spectrum of the original image $org(t, u)$. For simplification we need to take derivative of Eq. (2) reduced to Eq. (3) by computing DFT of original Image ($O(t, u)$) and DFT of noisy image ($N(t, u)$)

$$J = E \left[|O((t, u)) - H((t, u)) \cdot N((t, u))|^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$H(t, u) = \frac{E[N((t, u)) \cdot O^*((t, u))]}{E[|N((t, u))|^2]} \quad (4)$$

Here, the complex conjugate is denoted by *. In the case of the white noise availability, the numerator gets decreased as per Eq. (5). The denominator reduces as per Eq. (6). The Weiner filter's output is given as in Eq. (7) and (8), respectively. The inverse transform of DFT is IDFT. The pre-processed image I_{pre} is subjected to segmentation.

$$E[N(t, u) \cdot O^*(t, u)] = \begin{cases} = E\{[O(t, u) + N(t, u)] \times O^*(t, u)\} \\ = E\left[|O(t, u)|^2\right] \\ = P_D(t, u) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$E\left[|O((t, u))|^2\right] = P_D((t, u)) + P_N((t, u)) \quad (6)$$

This helps in increasing the quality of the image, by multiplying input image with Weiner filter as per Eq. (7) and resultant image presented as $Y(t, u)$.

$$Y(t, u) = H(t, u) \cdot I_{inp}(t, u) \quad (7)$$

Finally, wiener filter need to take Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT) as per Eq. (8).

$$y(t, u) = IDFT[Y(t, u)] \quad (8)$$

Subsequently, the resultant image of preprocessing using wiener filtering is to be passed for segmentation new Multi-Kernel K-Means clustering model

3.2 Multi-Kernel K-Means Model for Segmentation

The pre-processed images I_{pre} are segmented via the proposed Multi-Kernel K-Means Algorithm. The Multi-Kernel k-mean clustering is unsupervised. K-Means clustering algorithm is used to differentiate the interest region from the context based on the K-centroids; it clusters or partitions the given data into K-clusters or segments. It is predominantly used for clustering large sets of images into Region of Interest (ROI) and Non-ROI regions. The resolution of the image I_{pre} is (a, b) , which is clustered into k count of clusters. Let $I_{pre}(a, b)$ be the input pixel that is to be clustered and the cluster center is Cen_k . The steps followed in the k-means algorithm are below:

Algorithm: Multi-Kernel K-Means (I_{pre})

Step 1: Initialize the cluster center and the count of clusters k .

Step 2: Compute the Euclidean distance $Dist$ among every pixel in I_{pre} . In fact, using the relation below, the Euclidean distance between the image's center and each pixel is computed.

$$Dist = \|I_{pre}(a, b) - Cen_k\| \quad (9)$$

Step 3: Depending on the distance $Dist$, assign all pixels to the nearest center.

Step 4: Recalculate the new location of the center using the relation in Eq. (10), after all, pixels have been allocated.

$$Cen_k = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{a \in C_k} \sum_{b \in C_k} I_{pre}(a, b) \quad (10)$$

Step 5: Repeat the procedure before the tolerance or error value is met.

Step 6: Reshape the cluster pixels into the image.

While k-means has the advantage of being simple to be used, it does have some disadvantages. The final clustering results' consistency is determined by the random initial centroid selection. As a result, if the initial centroid is selected at random, the result would be different for different initial centers. Moreover, the K-means algorithm converges at a local minimum and it is highly computationally complex. So, we have introduced a new multi-kernel k-Means algorithm, where we've hybridized both the sigmoid and Laplacian kernel. Mathematically, Sigmoid and Laplacian kernel are shown in Eq. (11) and Eq. (12), respectively.

$$\text{Sigmoid kernel: } k_1(a, b) = \tanh(\beta_0 \langle a, b \rangle + \beta_1) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Laplacian kernel: } k_2(a, b) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|a - b\|}{\sigma}\right) \quad (12)$$

By combining Eq. (11) & (12) and by normalizing by Eq. (3) we are obtaining the cluster center using Eq. (13) and the segmented image thus obtained is denoted as I_{seg} , from which the multi-features are extracted.

$$k(a,b) = \frac{k_1 + k_2}{3} \quad (13)$$

3.3 Multi-Feature Extraction

The segmented image is denoted as I_{seg} , from which the multi-features (SURF, shape based features via canny edge detection model, gradient features via HOG and SIFT based features) are extracted. The features extracted from the segmented image and its relation with multi-feature extraction approach is as shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Feature Extraction

These additional features using SURF (f_{SURF}), shape based features via canny edge detection model (f_{can}), gradient features via HOG (f_{HOG}) and SIFT based features (f_{SIFT}) were extracted as below.

3.3.1. SURF (Speeded Up Robust Features)

The feature descriptions as well as feature extraction are the two major steps in the SURF model. In the feature extraction phase, the Hessian matrix approximation has been used for detecting the interest points. In (I_{seg}), the sum of values (pixel values) is computed in an effective manner using the Integral Image. In addition, it also computes the average intensity within I_{seg} at the location $R = (o, p)^T$; the Integral Image $Int_{\Sigma}(R)$ is computed as per Eq. (14).

$$Int_{\Sigma}(R) = \sum_{h=0}^{h \leq o} \sum_{g=0}^{g \leq p} Int(h, g) \quad (14)$$

The SURF descriptor is generated in two steps for the image as; at first repeatable orientation using data from a circular area surrounding the key point were established. The SURF descriptor is then extracted from a square region aligned to the chosen orientation. SURF attempts to find a reproducible orientation for the interest points in order to be rotation invariant for orientation assignments [28]. In order to perform this, SURF implies computation of Haar wavelet responses along X & Y directions of the segmented image as well as its circular neighborhood is also explored in the radius of 6's. The Hessian of this pixel (o, p) I_{seg} is denoted as per Eq. (15).

$$H(\text{Fun}(o, p)) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \text{fun}}{\partial o^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \text{fun}}{\partial o \partial p} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \text{fun}}{\partial o \partial p} & \frac{\partial^2 \text{fun}}{\partial p^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Partially differentiating Eq. (15), we get Eq. (16) as follows:

$$\text{The Hessian matrix } \mathfrak{N}(R, \gamma) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{oo}(R, \gamma) & G_{op}(R, \gamma) \\ G_{op}(R, \gamma) & G_{pp}(R, \gamma) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Here, $G_{oo}(R, \gamma)$ is the convolution corresponding to the 2nd order Gaussian derivative for I_{seg} in point R . In addition, $G_{op}(R, \gamma)$ and $G_{pp}(R, \gamma)$ points to the similarly. As a result, the wavelets are observed large at large scales due to which integral images can be used for quick filtering once more. In the second phase, the sums of vertically and horizontally wavelet responses are included in the scanning field, the scanning orientation is accordingly adjusted, and recalculate these attributes until the orientation with the highest sum value were not found, which is the key orientation of the function descriptor. The Descriptor Components represents the square area, created on the basis of centered key point aligned in the direction of the orientation. Isolated region is then divided into smaller 4* 4 square-shaped sub-regions on a constant basis. Naturally, at 5*5 regularly spaced sampling points were considered and useful in computation of sub-regions in the horizontal direction. The Haar wavelet responses referred to as d_x , while in the vertical direction it is referred to as d_y . In order to enhance the robustness against geometric deformations and localization errors, the responses d_x and d_y were weighted initially with a Gaussian ($\sigma = 3.3s$). Then, the wavelet responses d_x and d_y are summed up over each sub-region and form a first set of entries to the feature vector. In order to bring in information about the polarity of the intensity changes, the sum of the absolute values of the responses, $|d_x|$ and $|d_y|$ is also extracted. Hence, each sub-region has a four-dimensional descriptor vector v for its underlying intensity structure $V = (\sum d_x, \sum d_y, \sum |d_x|, \sum |d_y|)$. This results in a descriptor vector for all 4*4 sub-regions of length 64. The extracted SURF feature is denoted as f_{SURF} .

3.3.2. SIFT

The SIFT [29] feature is extracted from preprocessed image I_{pre} . In fact, the SIFT is indeed a simple procedure. The SIFT algorithm consists primarily of four stages, at first it concentrated towards Selection of a scale-space peak where it is the possible spot for locating features selected from the segmented image and defined by Eq. (17)

$$L(c, d, \sigma) = G(c, d, \sigma) * I_{\text{seg}}(c, d) \quad (17)$$

Where, $I_{\text{seg}}(c, d)$ is the segmented image with pixels (c, d) and $G(c, d, \sigma)$ is the Gaussian variable scale. In addition, $*$ points to the convolution operator to generate the key point in scale-space. However it was seen that, there are various method available for finding stable key point positions in the scale-space and one such technique is the difference of Gaussians, which

locates scale-space extrema, $U(c, d, \sigma)$ by computing the difference between two images, one with scale l times that of the other.

$$U(c, d, \sigma) = O(c, d, l\sigma) - O(c, d, \sigma) \quad (18)$$

Once stable key point in scale-space is located there is need of second step, key point Localization where the feature key points from the selected scale-space peak are localized accurately. The key points are generated in the previous phase resulted in a large number of key points, some of them seem to be too close to the edge, or there isn't enough contrast. They aren't as useful as features in this scenario, as a result it is necessary to get rid of such key points, and we get rid of them. The method is comparable to those used to suppress edge features in the Harris Corner Detector. The extrema location Q is given as per Eq. (19).

$$Q = \frac{\partial^2 U^{-1}}{\partial c^2} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial c} \quad (19)$$

After key point localization it is necessary to assign orientation to Key points depending on the scale. In order to do so, a neighborhood is drawn around the key point spot, and gradient magnitude and direction of the region were determined. The result is a 360-degree orientation histogram of 36 bins and its histogram is created. It was seen that, the peak in the histogram were found at some point. Hence, the orientation ϕ is computed as per Eq. (20).

$$\phi(c, d) = \tan(O(c, d + 1) - O(c, d - 1) / O(c + 1, d) - O(c - 1, y)) \quad (20)$$

The key point descriptor is required to be defined and it is done through high-dimensional vector that describes the key points. Each key point now has an attributes like position, size, and orientation. The next stage is to develop a descriptor for each key point's local image area which is strongly distinctive and as invariant as possible to changes in perspective as well as lighting and at last the function of key point matching is performed. The matching is performed on the basis of key point's closeness of between two images and such key points are paired.

At this point, each key point has a location, scale, orientation. Next is to compute a descriptor for the local image region about each key point that is highly distinctive and invariant as possible to variations such as changes in viewpoint and illumination. To do this, a 16x16 window around the key point is taken. It is divided into 16 sub-blocks of 4x4 sizes. For each sub-block, 8 bin orientation histogram is created. So 4 X 4 descriptors over 16 X 16 sample arrays were used in practice. 4 X 4 X 8 directions give 128 bin values. It is represented as a feature vector to form key point descriptor. The extracted SIFT feature is denoted as f_{SIFT} .

3.3.3. SHAPE FEATURES VIA CANNY EDGE DETECTION

The shape based features are extracted from I_{pre} . This computation is required to determine the shape of an object under observations and this can be effectively done with the use of canny edge detection [30]. The Canny edge detector recognizes a large variety of edges in images using a multi-stage algorithm (Canny Filter). To compute the intensity corresponding to the

image gradients, Canny employs a filter dependent on the derivative of a Gaussian. The Gaussian filter eliminates the influence of image noise by eliminating non-maximum pixels of the gradient magnitude, possible edges are thinned down to 1-pixel curves. Finally, using hysteresis thresholding on the gradient magnitude, edge pixels are retained or deleted. The general criteria for edge detection include edge detection with a low error rate, which ensures that the detection can recognize as much of the image's edges as possible. Similarly the operated sensed edge point should be effective in locating the edge's center and moreover image noise does not produce false edges in this case. The extracted shape base features via the canny edge detector are denoted as (f_{can}).

3.3.4. GRADIENT FEATURES VIA HOG

In I_{seg} , the HOG [31] (feature descriptor) identifies the homogeneous identical area and the features are computed using following steps

(a) Calculate the histogram of gradient directions or edge orientations of each pixel in each cell by dividing the pre-processed image into smaller related regions (referred to as cells).

For example, the image of 64x128 is divided into 8x8 cells. An 8x8 cell can simply be explained using 128 numbers (8x8x2 where the last 2 are from the gradient magnitude and directional values).

(b) Each cell is discretized into angular bins using gradient orientation.

For the histogram, each cell is split up into nine separate bins, each corresponding to angles from 0–160 in increments of 20.

(c) Each cell's pixel about its angular bin receives a weighted gradient.

(d) Consider a spatial region to be a group of adjacent cells (blocks).

The block histogram is formed by representing the Normalized type of histograms and is referred to as the descriptor. It is dependent on the classification and normalisation of histograms. The typical process of normalization occurs by simply calculating the length of a vector through its magnitude and then simply dividing all elements of that vector with the length. For example, if the vector is [1, 2, 3], then the length of the vector, using basic mathematical principles, would be the square root of 14. By dividing the vector by this length, new normalized vector thus obtained is [0.27, 0.53, 0.80]. The f_{HOG} represents the extracted HOG characteristics.

The overall extracted features are constituted in feature matrix denoted as

$$F = (f_{SURF}) + (f_{can}) + (f_{HOG}) + (f_{SIFT}).$$

The resultant matrix of feature is composed by the model vectors of (f_{SURF}), (f_{can}), (f_{HOG}), (f_{SIFT}), therefore in this case the problem of curse of dimensionality needs to be handled appropriately, so that the best optimal features from F can be derived and represented as F^* .

In order to address curse of dimensionality, a novel hybrid algorithm referred as PHSLA is used to achieve this optimum feature selection and these computed optimal features F^* are

given as input to Optimized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The weights of CNN are optimally tuned using the new PHSLA model to make target recognition more accurate. The PHSLA incorporates the principles of both PSO and SLnO on I_{seg} , segmented image.

4. DATASET

The dataset used for the simulation of the proposed model is Image Net [32]. To overcome the problem of overlapping objects as well as objects being camouflaged in the background it is necessary to enhance the performance of underlying algorithm to handle such complexity in object detection and classification Image Net dataset is found to be very useful. The data in this dataset is available for free to researchers for non-commercial use. Image Net dataset has 100,000 images across 200 classes. Each class has 500 training images, 50 validation images, and 50 test images provided with the labelling of images. The proposed ODMVI model is trained and evaluated over Image Net dataset. 10000 images of over 25 different categories were selected from the dataset for training the model. Initially most commonly used indoor objects were targeted and organized in to respective directories for training. The images were labelled with a string starting with 'n' preceded by a sequence of eight integers e.g. 'n03950228'. Every directory contained 400 different images of a particular object. The images were labelled with the name of directory preceded by underscore and sequence number e.g. 'n03950228_1, n03950228_2 etc.). After the complete analysis of CNN over the dataset, the model was trained to identify the objects with remarkable accuracy and precision.

5. OBJECT DETECTION VIA OPTIMIZED CNN USING PHSLA

The Deep neural networks have demonstrated their capacity to solve classification problems using a hierarchical model, there are millions of parameters, and learning with big datasets of Image Net. In order to utilize the multiple features set as well optimal features the CNN and PHSLA needs to be configured as below

5.1 CNN Architecture

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) are a special class of deep neural networks that consist of several convolutions, pooling, and fully connected layers; this has proven to be a robust method for image or video processing, classification, and pattern recognition. Fig.3 below depicts the schematic diagram of a basic convolutional neural network using proposed PHSLA for feature extraction as well as optimal tuning of weights of CNN for ODMVI.

Figure 3: Schematic Diagram of Optimized CNN+ PHSLA

As discussed in the earlier sections, the extracted F^* are given as input to optimized CNN for classifying the objects. Multiple layers of artificial neurons make up convolutional neural networks. Artificial neurons are mathematical functions that measure the weighted number of several inputs and emit an activation value, similar to their biological counterparts. Each neuron's action is determined by its weight. Therefore, we are fine-tuning the weights of CNN using a new PHSLA model to enhance the detection accuracy. The convolutional layer is pooling layer which is fully connected layer and has convolutional kernels in place. These convolutional kernel defines the entire function map in such a way that r^{th} layer of convolutional layer is mapped with z^{th} feature map as well feature values in the location provided to the CNN and being determined by Eq. (21).

$$S_{e,x,z}^r = W_z^r F_{e,x}^{*r} + B_z^r \quad (21)$$

$$AF_{e,x,z}^r = AF(S_{e,x,z}^r) \quad (22)$$

$$O_{e,x,z}^r = pool(AF_{e,x,z}^r), \forall (c,r) \in \mathfrak{R}_{e,x} \quad (23)$$

Where W_z^r and B_z^r are the optimum weight vector and bias, which provides the optimal tuning of the weights performed using the adopted hybrid optimization scheme. Similarly, $AF(\bullet)$ is activation function provides prediction of nonlinear features of multilayer networks and here it is used to achieve non-linearity and presented in Eq. 22, when processed provides activation value. The Shift variance in the pooling layer is handled by Eq. (23) and it deals with decreasing the resolution of induced feature map by local neighbourhood and presented by $pool(\cdot)$. The down sampling operations were also conducted by the pooling layer in CNN with the resultant collected from the convolutional layers. Additionally, maximum pooling and average pooling were also explored. The higher value was observed in the max-pooling; nevertheless, the average value was observed in the average pooling. Function loss be determined by using CNN as

$$Loss = \frac{1}{Num} \sum_{t=1}^{ms} G(\xi; V^{(t)}, OUT^{(t)}) \quad (24)$$

Where, (ξ) is the constraints of CNN are associated with required input-output relations and to be operated in limits of $\{(U^{(t)}, V^{(t)}); t \in [1, \dots, IO]\}$ and furthermore, output of CNN, t^{th} input data, and the related target values are determined as $OUT^{(t)}, U^{(t)}$ and $V^{(t)}$, correspondingly.

The results obtained from the pooling layer are usually given as an entry to the completely fully - connected, and hence the inputs are associated with both layers. The fully connected layer in the work appears at the output of the CNN system. The output layer of CNN is the final layer, and it includes the soft max function for performing precise final detection of objects in the images (targets). CNN's loss function ($Loss$) must be minimised in order to get the best result as per equation (25).

$$Obj = \min(Loss) \quad (25)$$

In order to have minimization of loss, the efforts were taken for fine-tuning the weight of CNN - w by the proposed PHSLA model. The obtained solution fed as input to PHSLA model with inputs of weight of CNN and extracted features, the method of solution encoding for PHSLA is as depicted in Fig.4.

5.2. PHSLA

The PSO is a Particle Swarm Optimization which is inspired by the activities populace of random solutions, and the quest for the best one is done by updating generations. The particles in this PSO are mainly engaged in a random location and are relocated in random definite directions inside the quest space. The selection of PSO has been good in solving complex optimization-related issues with higher accuracy and convergence rate. On the other hand, the SLnO algorithm is an iterative optimization technique based developing extremely sensitive features that have higher memory and at the same time, they search for the best solutions within the search space without getting caught into local optima [33-36]. Therefore, in the presented research work, these two algorithm were blended together to form Particle Hybridized Sea Lion Optimization Algorithm (PHSLA) to update the solutions with utmost precisions and higher convergence.

The steps followed in the PHSLA model is depicted below:

Step 1: The population P of search agents (sea lion and flock of birds) is initialized. In addition, the current iteration and the maximal iteration are denoted as itr & $\max^{itr}$ respectively.

Step 2: Initialize the N search agents with random velocities $V_i; i=1,2,\dots,N$ and position $X_i; i=1,2,\dots,N$

Step 3: Compute the fitness of the search agent using Eq. (25).

Step 5: Initialize $pbest$ with $X_i; i=1,2,\dots,N$

Step 6: Initialize $gbest$ with the best fitness search agent of $X_i; i=1,2,\dots,N$

Step 7: while $itr < \max^{itr}$ do

Step 8: update V_i^{itr} using Eq. (26).

$$V_i^{itr} = V_i^{itr} + 2 * rand * (pbest - X_i^{itr}) + 2 * rand * (gbest - X_i^{itr}) \quad (26)$$

Step 9: The proposed contribution is in this phase. In fact, the current position X_i^{itr} of the search agent has updated the standard PSO based positional update. Since the positional update with standard PSO sometimes gets traps into the local optima. Hence, we have updated the position of the search agent using a new update expression, which is based on SLnO's position update model. Thereby, the proposed algorithm has been named PHSLA. The proposed positional update of the search agent is given in Eq. (27).

$$X_i^{itr+1} = X_i^{itr} + ran_1 * (pbest - |X_i^{itr}|) + ran_2 * (gbest - |X_i^{itr}|) \quad (27)$$

Here, ran_1 and ran_2 are two random numbers within $[0, 1]$.

Step 10: In addition, we have introduced arithmetic cross-over operation, which is the second contribution. Following the velocity and position updates, each iteration undergoes a breeding phase. A crossover operator is being used to choose two particles at random for breeding at a user-specified breeding probability. Among the population, we have selected two particles A, B for performing the crossover operation. The position corresponding to X_A^{itr} and X_B^{itr} is replaced by the offspring. This is mathematically shown in Eq. (28) and Eq. (29), respectively.

$$X_A^{itr+1} = rad^{itr} * X_A^{itr} + (1 - rad^{itr}) * X_B^{itr} \quad (28)$$

$$X_B^{itr+1} = rad^{itr} * X_B^{itr} + (1 - rad^{itr}) * X_A^{itr} \quad (29)$$

Here, rad is a random number generated within the range $[0, 1]$. The velocities of these A, B particles are shown in Eq. (30) and Eq. (31), respectively.

$$V_A^{itr+1} = \frac{V_A^{itr} + V_B^{itr}}{\|V_A^{itr} + V_B^{itr}\|} \|V_A^{itr}\| \quad (30)$$

$$V_B^{itr+1} = \frac{V_A^{itr} + V_B^{itr}}{\|V_A^{itr} + V_B^{itr}\|} \|V_B^{itr}\| \quad (31)$$

Step 9: Compute the fitness of the search agent using Eq. (18). If the termination criterion is not met, increment the iteration itr by 1.

Step 10: Return the best solution

Step 11: Terminates

Algorithm 1: Pseudo code of PHSLA
Step1: Initialize P , $\max^{itr}$, itr
Step2: Initialize the N search agents with random velocities $V_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and position $X_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, N$
Step 3: Compute the fitness of the search agent using Eq. (25).
Step 4: Initialize $pbest$ with $X_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, N$
Step 5: Initialize $gbest$ with the best fitness search agent of $X_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, N$
Step 6: while $itr < \max^{itr}$ do
Update V_i^{itr} using Eq. (26).
Step 7: Update the position of the solutions by the proposed update equation as in Eq. (27)
Step 8: Perform arithmetic cross over operation
Step 9: Compute the fitness of the search agent using Eq. (25).
If the termination criterion is not met, increment the iteration itr by 1.
Step 10: Return the best solution
End while

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1. Simulation Procedure

The dataset used for the simulation of the proposed model is ImageNet. The proposed model (CNN+PHSLA) is evaluated over the existing models like CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLnO, CNN, and SVM in terms of “positive, negative and other measures”. This evaluation is carried out by varying the learning percentage from 60 (40% of data was used for training), 70 (30% of data was used for training), and 80 (20% of data was used for training), respectively. The positive measures like “accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, and precision” are ought to be sustained at a higher level, for the most favorable results. The error measures or native measures are FPR, FNR, and FDR, which need to be as low as possible. The F1-score, MCC, and NPV are additional value-added indicators that exhibit the supremacy of the proposed work. The sample image collected for evaluation is shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5: Sample and Segmented Images

6.2 Convergence Analysis

In order to understand the performance of the proposed model, it is expected that, proposed model has higher convergence towards the defined objective function. The outcomes of the convergence analysis of the proposed as well as existing models for each iteration are shown in Fig.6. Initially, at the least iteration count (at 0th iteration), the convergence of the proposed, as well as existing models, is higher. Then, as the count of iteration gets increased gradually, the cost of the proposed, as well as existing models tends to be decreased. Eventually, the proposed method achieves minimum fitness values while comparing with the traditional methods. Further, at the maximum iteration of 50, the proposed method attains fewer fitness values. Thus, from the observation, it is observed that the CNN+PHSLA can reduce the loss of CNN, which represents the detection accuracy of the proposed model has attained its supremacy.

Figure 6: Convergence Analysis

6.3 Performance Evaluation of CNN+PHSLA

As discussed earlier, proposed model's outcome (CNN+PHSLA) is assessed using positive, negative, and other measures. Fig. 7& Fig. 8 depict the results obtained in terms of positive measures accuracy and precision respectively. Based on the obtained results, the CNN+PHSLA

are considered to be very beneficial, as it has archived the highest value for every variation in the learning percentage. The accuracy, which is the most important metric, reveals the superiority of the CNN+PHSLA. Remarkably, with any shift in the learning percentage, the accuracy of the planned work has been shown to be higher. Furthermore, the planned work had attained the best accuracy even at the highest learning percentage (i.e. 80 percent). The accuracy of the CNN+PHSLA at learning percentage=80 is 77.78%, which is better than the existing models like CNN+PSO=66.67%, CNN+WOA=50%, CNN+GWO=54.16%, CNN + SLnO=62.50%, CNN=55.56% and SVM=62.50%.

Table 1: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of Accuracy

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.708333	0.666667	0.666667	0.611111	0.472222	0.611111	0.666667
70	0.583333	0.62963	0.694444	0.62963	0.555556	0.694444	0.740741
80	0.666667	0.5	0.541667	0.625	0.555556	0.625	0.777778

Figure 7: Performance of Adopted Method Over Extant Models for Accuracy

In addition, the precision, sensitivity as well as specificity of the CNN+PHSLA are found to be higher for every variation in learning percentage. Among all these an interesting outcome has been recorded in case of precision. The precision of the proposed model is 66.67% at the highest learning percentage, which is indeed a favourable score. At 80th learning percentage, the precision of the work with fusion approach is found to be for CNN+PSO=33.33%, CNN+WOA=0, CNN+GWO=8.33%, CNN+SLnO=25%, CNN=33.33%, SVM=25%, and CNN+PHSLA=66.67% respectively. The performance of CNN+PHSLA is observed to be outperforming than the existing works reported combinations of CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLnO, CNN and SVM. In addition, the sensitivity of the proposed work at 70th learning is found to be 61.11% where are other fusion performance are as 16.67%, 44.44%, 38.89%, 44.44%, 33.33%, 38.89% for CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLnO, CNN, and SVM, respectively. Thus, from the evaluation, it's clear that the

proposed work had archived maximal values in terms of positive performance measures, and this is said to be the most favourable outcome.

Table 2: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of Precision

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.416667	0.333333	0.333333	0.416667	0.208333	0.416667	0.5
70	0.166667	0.444444	0.388889	0.444444	0.333333	0.388889	0.611111
80	0.333333	0	0.083333	0.25	0.333333	0.25	0.666667

Figure 8: Performance of Adopted Method Over Extant Models for Precision

6.4 Overall Performance Analysis

The accuracy of the CNN+PHSLA at 80th learning percentage is 0.78, which's the highest value when compared to existing works like CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLO, CNN and SVM. In addition, the precision of the CNN+PHSLA at 80th learning percentage is 0.67, which is better than the existing works like CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLO, CNN, and SVM, respectively. In addition, the CNN+PHSLA has archived the least error measures. On the other hand, the FDR of the CNN+PHSLA is 0.33 (Table 4), which is the least value when compared to traditional works like CNN+PSO=0.67, CNN+WOA=1, CNN+GWO=0.92, CNN+SLO=0.75, CNN=0.67, and SVM=0.75, respectively. Moreover, F1-score (Table 5), MCC (Table 6), and NPV (Table 7) are found to be higher with the CNN+PHSLA for every variation in the learning percentage. From the overall evaluation, it is clear that the CNN+PHSLA had achieved the optimal values, thereby the CNN+PHSLA had become much sufficient for detecting the objects. Table 3. below summarizes the performance analysis of CNN+PHSLA at the 80th learning percentage for the measures accuracy and precision.

Table 3: Performance analysis of CNN+PHSLA for Accuracy and Precision

Method	Accuracy	Precision
CNN+PSO	0.666667	0.333333
CNN+WOA	0.5	0
CNN+GWO	0.541667	0.083333
CNN+SLO	0.625	0.25
CNN	0.555556	0.333333
SVM	0.625	0.25
CNN+PHSLA	0.777778	0.666667

Table 4: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of FDR

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.583333	0.666667	0.666667	0.583333	0.791667	0.583333	0.5
70	0.833333	0.555556	0.611111	0.555556	0.666667	0.611111	0.388889
80	0.666667	1	0.916667	0.75	0.666667	0.75	0.333333

Table 5: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of F1-Score

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.416667	0.333333	0.333333	0.416667	0.208333	0.416667	0.5
70	0.166667	0.444444	0.388889	0.444444	0.333333	0.388889	0.611111
80	0.333333	NaN	0.083333	0.25	0.333333	0.25	0.666667

Table 6: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of MCC

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.222222	0.111111	0.111111	0.125	-0.1875	0.125	0.25
70	-0.111111	0.166667	0.185185	0.166667	0	0.185185	0.416667
80	0.111111	-0.333333	-0.222222	0	0	0	0.5

Table 7: Performance Analysis of Proposed and Conventional Work in terms of NPV

Learning Rate	CNN+PSO	CNN+WOA	CNN+GWO	CNN+SLO	CNN	SVM	CNN+PHSLA
60	0.805556	0.777778	0.777778	0.708333	0.604167	0.708333	0.75
70	0.722222	0.722222	0.796296	0.722222	0.666667	0.796296	0.805556
80	0.777778	0.666667	0.694444	0.75	0.666667	0.75	0.833333

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this research work, the proposed model will act as black box for the system developed on top for assisting visually challenged. The proposed work meticulously consider the development of system in major phases including pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, optimal feature selection and object detection. . The optimal features were mined from the extracted features using a new hybrid algorithm (PHSLA). These optimal features were fed as the input to Optimized CNN for object detection mechanism. In order to make the object detection more precise, the weights of CNN are optimally tuned using a new hybrid model. The proposed hybrid model referred to as PHSLA, which combines the power of both PSO and SLnO, respectively. The accuracy of the CNN+PHSLA at learning percentage=80 is 77.78%, which is better than the existing models like CNN+PSO, CNN+WOA, CNN+GWO, CNN+SLnO, CNN and SVM. From the overall evaluation, it is clear that the CNN+PHSLA had achieved the optimal values; thereby the CNN+PHSLA had become much efficient for detecting the objects. The current research work has emphasized assisting visually impaired people by helping them identify the objects in their environment. The work will be extended towards detection of multiple objects in unconstrained environment or in the vicinity of the stationary viewer and giving them aural notifications regarding the multiple objects.

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